

Free Energy When It Is Used Twice

We are a group of nine people. In May 2026, we filed a patent application for the invention illustrated in the accompanying figure.

It is a well-known principle that energy cannot be created from nothing. In fact, the operation of this invention is based on using energy that already exists and making use of it a second time.

Consider a weight dropped from a certain height onto a cylindrical metal spring. The weight will rebound, typically losing about 20% of its energy.

Now consider the mechanism shown in the figure, which is a top view and therefore excludes the effects of gravity.

We arrange the system as described above and observe and measure how much the spring is compressed when the weight, under a normal working force, strikes the base directly (without the small cylinder). During the rebound, the weight loses approximately 20% of its energy.

Next, a hole is made in the base to accommodate a small cylinder that protrudes 9 cm above the surface of the base. On its lower end, the cylinder is rigidly connected to a gear that rotates freely on its own shaft. This gear meshes with a second gear that is fixed to its own rotating shaft. The mechanism operates so that each time the cylinder is actuated, it is equivalent to giving a half pedal stroke on a bicycle. As a result, the rotating shaft drives a dynamo, which generates electrical energy.

After measuring the spring compression when the weight strikes the base directly—for example, X cm—we then adjust the system so that the spring acts on the cylinder until it compresses by $9/10$ of X . Consequently, only the remaining $1/10$ of X of the force is applied directly to the base.

According to our hypothesis, the rebound should remain the same, or nearly the same, while the cylinder will have recovered approximately 90% of the gross energy. The next step is to determine whether the net recovered energy is sufficient both to restore the energy lost by the weight for the normal continuation of the cycle and, possibly, to produce some surplus energy as an additional output.

We believe this may be possible, although extensive experimental testing will certainly be required. Our reasoning is that a mechanism of this kind may be capable of using the same existing energy twice.

The right-hand side of the figure is shown with a different design to illustrate that the rebound mechanism can be implemented in various ways.

We would appreciate any comments, technical opinions, or possible proposals regarding this concept.

